

Table S1: Bird species occurrence and abundance across the study strata with habitat affiliation, foraging layer, and diet guild categories. Tabled values are number of detections (number of individuals). Key: RF – rainforest species; OC – open country species; AER – aerial; AQU – aquatic; CAN – canopy; SHR – shrub; MID – mid-storey; TER – Terrestrial.

Species	Habitat Affiliation	Foraging layer	Diet guild	Conventional Tea	Organic tea	Mixed shade tea	Rainforest fragment	Continuous rainforest
Ashy Drongo <i>Dicrurus leucophaeus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	2 (2)	4 (5)	11 (15)	3 (3)	2 (2)
Ashy Prinia <i>Prinia socialis</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	-	8 (11)	1 (1)	-	-
Ashy Woodswallow <i>Artamus fuscus</i>	OC	AER	Invertebrate	1 (2)	2 (4)	-	-	-
Asian Brown Flycatcher <i>Muscicapa dauurica</i>	OC	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	4 (4)	3 (3)	-
Asian Fairy-Bluebird <i>Irena puella</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	-	6 (6)	8 (9)
Asian Paradise-Flycatcher <i>Terpsiphone paradisi</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	3 (3)
Bar-winged Flycatcher-Shrike <i>Hemipus picatus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	2 (4)
Besra <i>Accipiter virgatus</i>	RF	CAN	Bird of prey	-	-	-	-	1 (1)
Black-and-rufous Flycatcher <i>Ficedula nigrorufa</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	6 (8)
Black-naped Monarch <i>Hypothymis azurea</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	2 (2)
Black-rumped Flameback <i>Dinopium benghalense</i>	OC	MID	Invertebrate	1 (1)	4 (4)	5 (5)	2 (2)	-
Black-shouldered Kite <i>Elanus caeruleus</i>	OC	TER	Bird of prey	1 (1)	1 (1)	-	-	-
Black-throated Munia <i>Lonchura kelaarti</i>	RF	SHR	Plant + seed	-	-	-	-	1 (3)
Blyth's Reed-Warbler <i>Acrocephalus dumetorum</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	115 (115)	124 (128)	94 (94)	28 (28)	32 (34)
Bronzed Drongo <i>Dicrurus aeneus</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	1 (1)	1 (1)
Brown Shrike <i>Lanius cristatus</i>	OC	TER	Invertebrate	3 (3)	9 (10)	8 (8)	-	-
Brown-breasted Flycatcher <i>Muscicapa muttui</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	3 (3)
Brown-capped Woodpecker <i>Yungipicus nanus</i>	OC	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	1 (1)	2 (2)	-
Brown-cheeked Fulvetta <i>Alcippe poioicephala</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	19 (44)
Cattle Egret <i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	OC	AQU	Invertebrate	-	2 (2)	-	-	-

Species	Habitat Affiliation	Foraging layer	Diet guild	Conventional Tea	Organic tea	Mixed shade tea	Rainforest fragment	Continuous rainforest
Chestnut-headed Bee-eater <i>Merops leschenaulti</i>	OC	AER	Invertebrate	7 (9)	5 (8)	9 (16)	12 (21)	1 (2)
Chestnut-tailed Starling <i>Sturnia malabarica</i>	OC	CAN	Omnivore	-	-	2 (19)	-	-
Common Buzzard <i>Buteo buteo</i>	OC	CAN	Bird of prey	-	1 (1)	-	-	-
Common Flameback <i>Dinopium javanense</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	1 (4)
Common Iora <i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	OC	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	1 (5)	-	-
Common Kingfisher <i>Alcedo atthis</i>	OC	AQU	Bird of prey	1 (1)	-	1 (1)	-	-
Common Rosefinch <i>Carpodacus erythrinus</i>	OC	CAN	Plant + seed	-	1 (1)	18 (63)	-	-
Common Tailorbird <i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	13 (15)	12 (14)	11 (14)	3 (3)	1 (1)
Crested Serpent-Eagle <i>Spilornis cheela</i>	RF	CAN	Bird of prey	-	2 (3)	2 (3)	1 (1)	-
Crimson-backed Sunbird <i>Leptocoma minima</i>	RF	CAN	Omnivore	-	-	2 (2)	6 (7)	34 (42)
Dark-fronted Babbler <i>Rhopocichla atriceps</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	5 (9)
Dusky Crag-Martin <i>Ptyonoprogne concolor</i>	OC	AER	Invertebrate	3 (6)	-	-	-	-
Emerald Dove <i>Chalcophaps indica</i>	RF	TER	Omnivore	-	-	-	3 (3)	2 (2)
Eurasian Hoopoe <i>Upupa epops</i>	OC	TER	Invertebrate	6 (7)	-	1 (1)	-	-
Forest Wagtail <i>Dendronanthus indicus</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	-
Golden-fronted Leafbird <i>Chloropsis aurifrons</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	1 (2)	-	9 (10)	1 (2)	-
Gray Junglefowl <i>Gallus sonneratii</i>	RF	TER	Omnivore	2 (3)	2 (2)	15 (17)	6 (6)	6 (6)
Gray Wagtail <i>Motacilla cinerea</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	9 (9)	5 (5)	11 (11)	-	3 (3)
Gray-breasted Prinia <i>Prinia hodgsonii</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	-	1 (2)	2 (3)	-	-
Gray-fronted Green-Pigeon <i>Treron affinis</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	2 (2)	12 (17)	1 (1)
Gray-headed Canary-Flycatcher <i>Culicicapa ceylonensis</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	11 (11)
Great Hornbill <i>Buceros bicornis</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	-	1 (1)	-
Greater Coucal <i>Centropus sinensis</i>	OC	SHR	Omnivore	2 (2)	6 (9)	2 (2)	2 (2)	-
Greater Flameback <i>Chrysocolaptes guttacristatus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	4 (5)	3 (5)

Species	Habitat Affiliation	Foraging layer	Diet guild	Conventional Tea	Organic tea	Mixed shade tea	Rainforest fragment	Continuous rainforest
Greater Racket-tailed Drongo <i>Dicrurus paradiseus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	1 (1)	24 (28)	4 (5)
Greenish Warbler <i>Phylloscopus trochiloides</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	27 (27)	17 (17)	43 (43)	32 (34)	44 (44)
House Crow <i>Corvus splendens</i>	OC	TER	Bird of prey	-	7 (11)	-	-	-
House Sparrow <i>Passer domesticus</i>	OC	TER	Plant + seed	-	2 (3)	-	-	-
Indian Blackbird <i>Turdus simillimus</i>	RF	CAN	Omnivore	-	2 (2)	9 (10)	2 (4)	1 (1)
Indian Blue Robin <i>Larvivora brunnea</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	-	-	3 (3)	3 (3)	1 (1)
Indian Golden Oriole <i>Oriolus kundoo</i>	OC	CAN	Omnivore	-	4 (6)	2 (2)	-	-
Indian Peafowl <i>Pavo cristatus</i>	OC	TER	Plant + seed	-	2 (7)	-	-	-
Indian Pitta <i>Pitta brachyura</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	2 (2)	1 (1)	1 (1)	-	-
Indian Pond-Heron <i>Ardeola grayii</i>	OC	AQU	Omnivore	5 (5)	2 (2)	4 (4)	1 (1)	-
Indian Scimitar-Babbler <i>Pomatorhinus horsfieldii</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	7 (13)	11 (19)	12 (22)	10 (13)	20 (36)
Indian Swiftlet <i>Aerodramus unicolor</i>	RF	AER	Invertebrate	-	-	5 (125)	-	2 (4)
Indian Tit <i>Machlolophus aplonotus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	1 (1)	2 (4)	5 (5)	4 (8)
Intermediate Egret <i>Ardea intermedia</i>	OC	AQU	Bird of prey	1 (1)	-	-	-	-
Jungle Myna <i>Acridotheres fuscus</i>	OC	TER	Omnivore	35 (94)	65 (120)	3 (7)	-	1 (2)
Large-billed Crow <i>Corvus macrorhynchos</i>	OC	TER	Omnivore	19 (24)	22 (38)	2 (2)	13 (25)	1 (2)
Large-billed Leaf Warbler <i>Phylloscopus magnirostris</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	-	12 (12)	35 (35)
Legge's Hawk-Eagle <i>Nisaetus kelaarti</i>	RF	CAN	Bird of prey	-	-	-	1 (1)	-
Little Cormorant <i>Microcarbo niger</i>	OC	AQU	Bird of prey	1 (1)	-	-	-	-
Little Spiderhunter <i>Arachnothera longirostra</i>	RF	MID	Omnivore	-	-	-	1 (1)	8 (8)
Long-tailed Shrike <i>Lanius schach</i>	OC	TER	Invertebrate	4 (4)	19 (20)	-	-	-
Malabar Barbet <i>Psilopogon malabaricus</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	10 (13)	34 (40)	5 (5)
Malabar Gray Hornbill <i>Ocyceros griseus</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	1 (1)	12 (15)	2 (2)

Species	Habitat Affiliation	Foraging layer	Diet guild	Conventional Tea	Organic tea	Mixed shade tea	Rainforest fragment	Continuous rainforest
Malabar Parakeet <i>Psittacula columboides</i>	RF	CAN	Plant + seed	-	1 (1)	-	1 (2)	-
Malabar Trogon <i>Harpactes fasciatus</i>	RF	MID	Invertebrate	-	-	-	1 (1)	-
Malabar Whistling-Thrush <i>Myophonus horsfieldii</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	6 (6)	4 (5)	16 (16)	29 (31)	10 (10)
Mountain Imperial-Pigeon <i>Ducula badia</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	-	3 (4)	21 (23)
Nilgiri Flowerpecker <i>Dicaeum concolor</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	3 (3)	60 (66)	55 (63)	32 (37)
Nilgiri Flycatcher <i>Eumyias albicaudatus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	8 (11)
Orange Minivet <i>Pericrocotus flammeus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	2 (6)	-	9 (22)	19 (69)	6 (11)
Orange-headed Thrush <i>Geokichla citrina</i>	RF	TER	Omnivore	-	-	8 (10)	9 (10)	3 (4)
Oriental Magpie-Robin <i>Copsychus saularis</i>	OC	TER	Invertebrate	44 (53)	31 (42)	21 (26)	6 (9)	-
Oriental White-Eye <i>Zosterops palpebrosus</i>	RF	CAN	Omnivore	1 (4)	8 (21)	24 (66)	13 (41)	34 (101)
Pied Bushchat <i>Saxicola caprata</i>	OC	TER	Invertebrate	1 (1)	-	-	-	-
Plum-headed Parakeet <i>Psittacula cyanocephala</i>	OC	CAN	Fruit + nectar	14 (17)	3 (4)	18 (27)	6 (10)	-
Puff-throated Babbler <i>Pellorneum ruficeps</i>	RF	TER	Invertebrate	-	-	6 (6)	6 (9)	22 (37)
Purple Sunbird <i>Cinnyris asiaticus</i>	OC	CAN	Fruit + nectar	2 (2)	5 (7)	10 (13)	6 (7)	-
Red Spurfowl <i>Galloperdix spadicea</i>	RF	TER	Omnivore	2 (3)	-	1 (1)	1 (1)	-
Red-breasted Flycatcher <i>Ficedula parva</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	1 (1)	-	-
Red-rumped Swallow <i>Cecropis daurica</i>	OC	AER	Invertebrate	-	2 (5)	-	-	-
Red-vented Bulbul <i>Pycnonotus cafer</i>	OC	MID	Omnivore	2 (8)	-	-	-	-
Red-whiskered Bulbul <i>Pycnonotus jocosus</i>	OC	MID	Omnivore	68 (102)	67 (121)	81 (148)	9 (14)	12 (23)
Rufous Babbler <i>Turdoides subrufa</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	3 (6)	8 (25)	14 (28)	1 (2)	-
Rusty-tailed Flycatcher <i>Ficedula ruficauda</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	2 (2)	-
Small Minivet <i>Pericrocotus cinnamomeus</i>	OC	CAN	Invertebrate	1 (4)	-	3 (6)	1 (5)	-
Southern Hill Myna <i>Gracula indica</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	8 (21)	32 (61)	3 (4)
Speckled Piculet <i>Picumnus innominatus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	1 (1)

Species	Habitat Affiliation	Foraging layer	Diet guild	Conventional Tea	Organic tea	Mixed shade tea	Rainforest fragment	Continuous rainforest
Spotted Dove <i>Streptopelia chinensis</i>	OC	TER	Plant + seed	29 (34)	55 (72)	20 (24)	9 (12)	2 (2)
Square-tailed Bulbul <i>Hypsipetes ganeesa</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	-	-	-	-	27 (51)
Streak-throated Woodpecker <i>Picus xanthopygaeus</i>	OC	MID	Invertebrate	2 (2)	14 (16)	7 (8)	-	-
Thick-billed Warbler <i>Arundinax aedon</i>	OC	SHR	Invertebrate	1 (1)	6 (6)	-	-	-
Velvet-fronted Nuthatch <i>Sitta frontalis</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	1 (2)	7 (11)	13 (22)	10 (19)
Verditer Flycatcher <i>Eumyias thalassinus</i>	RF	CAN	Invertebrate	-	-	-	-	1 (1)
Vernal Hanging-Parrot <i>Loriculus vernalis</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	2 (2)	-	5 (5)	14 (16)	2 (2)
White-bellied Blue-Flycatcher <i>Cyornis pallidipes</i>	RF	SHR	Invertebrate	-	-	-	3 (4)	7 (10)
White-breasted Waterhen <i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	OC	AQU	Omnivore	-	2 (2)	1 (1)	-	-
White-cheeked Barbet <i>Psilopogon viridis</i>	RF	CAN	Fruit + nectar	3 (4)	11 (13)	45 (60)	29 (36)	25 (32)
White-throated Kingfisher <i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	OC	AQU	Bird of prey	1 (1)	-	4 (4)	2 (2)	-
Yellow-browed Bulbul <i>Iole indica</i>	RF	MID	Omnivore	-	-	2 (3)	16 (23)	49 (83)
Unidentified				3 (3)	1 (1)	4 (5)	13 (16)	10 (10)